

Proofs for parameter calculation for isotropic kernels with uniform dilation of 1

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For a channel multiplier $m \in \mathbb{N}$, I try to show one can have an algorithm which can find parameters stride, input padding, output padding, where output size s is a multiple of input size by factor of m , alternatively one can set the output dimension to be $m \times$ input dimension and figure out the rest of the parameters: stride, input padding and output padding correctly. Code available at <https://github.com/grussdorjan/convtranspose3d-params>

1 ConvTranspose3D

The formula for output dimension in ConvTranspose3D is given by (see [1, 2])

$$D_{out} = (D_{in} - 1) \times \text{stride}[0] - 2 \times \text{padding}[0] + \text{dilation}[0] \times (\text{kernel_size}[0] - 1) + \text{output_padding}[0] + 1 \quad (1)$$

$$H_{out} = (H_{in} - 1) \times \text{stride}[1] - 2 \times \text{padding}[1] + \text{dilation}[1] \times (\text{kernel_size}[1] - 1) + \text{output_padding}[1] + 1 \quad (2)$$

$$W_{out} = (W_{in} - 1) \times \text{stride}[2] - 2 \times \text{padding}[2] + \text{dilation}[2] \times (\text{kernel_size}[2] - 1) + \text{output_padding}[2] + 1 \quad (3)$$

For simplicity fix dilation d to be 1 and considering a cubic (isotropic) kernel where $D_{out} = W_{out} = H_{out} =$ output size, O_s

s : stride

p : padding

k : kernel size

i : input size

o_p : output padding

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Simplifying we have the following formula

$$O_s = (i - 1) \times s - 2 \times p + d \cdot (k - 1) + o_p + 1$$

Note whenever padding p is mentioned, I mean input padding unless explicitly stated as output padding o_p .

1.1 For fixed stride of 2, specific case for doubling spatial dimension

Hypothesis:

stride = 2 fixed for doubling

even kernel: $p = \lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor - 1, o_p = 0$

odd kernel: $p = \lfloor \frac{k-1}{2} \rfloor, o_p = 1$

We want: output dim = 2 × input dim, for odd kernel size case:

$$\begin{aligned} & (i - 1)2 - 2 \lfloor \frac{k-1}{2} \rfloor + k - 1 + 1 + 1 \\ (i - 1)2 - 2 \lfloor \frac{2m+1-1}{2} \rfloor + [(2m + 1) - 1] + 1 + 1, (k = 2m + 1, m \in \mathbb{N}_0) \\ & (i - 1)2 - 2 \lfloor \frac{2m}{2} \rfloor + 2m + 1 + 1 \\ & (i - 1)2 - 2m + 2m + 2 \\ & (i - 1)2 + 2 \\ & 2i - 2 + 2 \\ & 2i \end{aligned}$$

Again for output dim = 2 × input dim, for even kernel size case:

$$\begin{aligned} & (i - 1)2 - 2(\lfloor \frac{k}{2} \rfloor - 1) + k - 1 + 0 + 1 \text{ (output padding = 0)} \\ (i - 1)2 - 2(\lfloor \frac{2m}{2} \rfloor - 1) + 2m, (k = 2m, m \in \mathbb{N}_0) \\ & (i - 1)2 - 2(m - 1) + 2m \\ & 2i - 2 - 2m + 2 + 2m \\ & 2i \end{aligned}$$

1.2 General Case

However if we want a more generic solution we can consider the following algorithm:

1.3 Proof

Formula for output size is

$$(i - 1)s - 2p + d(k - 1) + o_p + 1$$

which becomes

$$(i - 1)s - 2p + k + o_p \quad [:\cdot d = 1]$$

Algorithm 1 GetConvTranspose3DParams

Require: i : input size, m : output multiplier, k : kernel size**Ensure:** s : stride, p : input padding, o_p : output padding, O_s : output size

```
1:  $s \leftarrow m$ 
2:  $o_t \leftarrow m \cdot i$  ▷ Target output size
3: for  $o_p \in \{0, 1\}$  do
4:    $n \leftarrow (i - 1)s + (k - 1) + o_p + 1 - o_t$ 
5:   if  $n \bmod 2 = 0$  then
6:      $p \leftarrow n/2$ 
7:     if  $p \geq 0$  then
8:        $O_s \leftarrow (i - 1) \cdot s - 2 \cdot p + (k - 1) + o_p + 1$ 
9:       return  $(s, p, o_p, O_s)$ 
10:    end if
11:  end if
12: end for
13: return error: No valid padding/output_padding combination found
```

The algorithm sets $s = m$ and seeks to achieve output size $i \cdot m$

1.4 Deriving the core equation

We need:

$$(i - 1)m - 2p + k + o_p = i \cdot m$$

Simplifying:

$$im - m - 2p + k + o_p = im$$

$$k + o_p - m = 2p$$

This is a fundamental constraint, the algorithm must find integers $p \geq 0$ and $o_p \in \{0, 1\}$ satisfying this equation. We are calculating a factor **numerator** as $\text{numerator} = (i - 1)m + (k - 1) + o_p + 1 - im = k + o_p - m$. Important note is that the i term cancels completely. The input size i is irrelevant to whether valid parameters exist. The algorithm checks

1. Is the numerator even
2. Is the numerator ≥ 0 (as $p = \frac{\text{numerator}}{2} \geq 0$, i.e. padding must be ≥ 0 , no floor division required as the numerator must be even to reach this stage)

2 Main theorem

2.1 Theorem

The algorithm succeeds **if and only if** $k \geq m - 1$. When it succeeds, the returned parameters are correct.

2.2 Proof

Part 1: Existence of Valid output Padding

Lemma 1: For any integers k, m there exists exactly one $o_p \in \{0, 1\}$ such that $k + o_p - m$ is even.

Proof: Consider $k - m$

- If $k - m$ is even, then $o_p = 0$ works: $k + 0 - m$ is even
- If $k - m$ is odd, then $o_p = 1$ works: $k + 1 - m$ is even (adding 1 flips parity)

These are mutually exclusive, so exactly one o_p works.

Part 2: Non negativity condition

Lemma 2: The algorithm succeeds iff $k + o_p \geq m$ for the o_p from Lemma 1.

Proof: The algorithm requires numerator $= k + o_p - m \geq 0$ which is equivalent to $k + o_p \geq m$. By Lemma 1, parity is always achievable, so this is the only remaining condition.

Part 3: Success condition

Lemma 3: $k + o_p \geq m$ is equivalent to $k \geq m - 1$

Proof:

- **Case** $k \geq m$, then $k + o_p \geq m + o_p \geq m$ (Since $o_p \geq 0$)
- **Case** $k = m - 1$, then $k - m = -1$ (odd case), so Lemma 1 gives $o_p = 1$. Thus $k + o_p = (m - 1) + 1 = m \geq m$
- **Case** $k \leq m - 2$, then for both $o_p = 0$ and $o_p = 1$, $k + o_p \leq m - 1 \leq m$

Thus, the condition holds **iff** $k \geq m - 1$

Part 4: Correctness of returned parameters

Lemma 4: When the algorithm succeeds, the returned parameters achieve exactly $i \cdot m$ output size.

Proof: When successful, the algorithm returns $p = \frac{k + o_p - m}{2}$. Further $s = m$, o_p is chosen from Lemma 1 and k is specified. Important note here is in the algorithm we are already checking whether numerator is even, and then we divide it by two. Substituting into the output formula output =

$$\begin{aligned} & (i - 1)m - 2 \frac{k + o_p - m}{2} + k + o_p \\ &= im - m - k - o_p + m + k + o_p = im \end{aligned}$$

Thus by Lemma 3, the algorithm succeeds iff $k \geq m - 1$ and by Lemma 4, when it succeeds, the parameters are correct.

References

- [1] Vincent Dumoulin and Francesco Visin. “A guide to convolution arithmetic for deep learning”. In: *arXiv preprint arXiv:1603.07285* (2016).
- [2] Pytorch Team. *torch.nn.ConvTranspose3d — PyTorch 2.10 documentation*. Accessed: 2026-02-05. URL: <https://docs.pytorch.org/docs/stable/generated/torch.nn.ConvTranspose3d.html>.